

ISic0614

I.Sicily inscription 0614

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

stone

Object

moulding

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Ietas

Place of origin (modern)

Monte Iato

Provenance

On the partially preserved moulding of the rostra/tribunal in the internal NW corner of the north portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.967305, 13.198057

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Monte Iato

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cn(aeus) Host[ilius][---]

Apparatus

Text from photograph

Translation

Commentary

Hosticius is also theoretically possible as a name, but much less common. The case of the name, nominative, accusative, or dative is unknowable, as is the precise function of the inscription.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491380

EDCS 380313

Bibliography

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